

Computing in the clouds – flexibility for a world in movement

The whole world is becoming mobile: today, we can read our electronic mail not only at work, but also on the PC at home or on the mobile on the move. And when we are on the train, we want to be able to access on our mobile those music tracks that we downloaded to our home computer. Therefore, more and more data is being stored on the net, on platforms that allow them to be saved there and called up again later. The software is also moveable: instead of installing it on a device, more and more users are acquiring appropriate programmes from the web. «Cloud Computing» is when files and programmes are not saved on a computer but are instead saved and/or obtained on the internet.

- **What does «Cloud Computing» mean for data security?**
- **What are the technical requirements for this, and what consequences could arise for society, the economy and the environment?**
- **Is Cloud Computing even something new?**

The Centre for technology assessment TA-SWISS called up a panel of experts to answer these questions. This fact sheet summarises the results of that discussion.

Revolution or Evolution?

Cloud Computing is the result of various technical developments. The fact that IT already started to develop network structures in the 1950s, which focussed on offering services on the server that could be requested by the client, demonstrates one of the requirements for Cloud Computing. The work distribution between server and client was taken even further with the concept of «thin client»: the end device is reduced to the basics, so that users are no longer in a position to make mistakes. Users limit themselves to entering their data, while the processing takes place in a central computing unit. Therefore, demands and requirements on servers increased, and so did their capabilities.

For individual companies, a fixed stock of high-performance servers has disadvantages: apart from the costs of acquisition and maintenance, the adaptability is also limited, in order to react to the variations in demand. Therefore the work is increasingly carried out in so-called «clusters»: computers are connected together through a fast network, to make whole «swarms», so that idle capacities can be used in places where the need for performance is higher. Cluster structures therefore enable dynamic planning, depending on the demand. In the so-called «grid» – a mix of clusters, which work together on one task – this form of technical cooperation peaks: a super computer emerges, which can process the huge amount of data which occurs, for instance, in the high profile research experiments performed by the European Organization for Nuclear Research CERN.

While in the past different devices were needed for various activities such as telephoning, writing or listening to music, today electronic gadgets are diverse all-rounders: videos and TV programmes can be played on the laptop, while the Smartphone can also be used to write texts, check emails or take photographs. This so-called «convergence of end devices» is a further drive for Cloud Computing. In order that these different applications function on various platforms, uniform standards are required, which allow the exchange of the most diverse data. At the same time a requirement for virtualisation is also fulfilled, which allows certain services to be simulated: in this way users get the impression that they are moving in a homogeneous IT environment, although in reality the most diverse applications and programmes are virtually merged into a unit.

Cloud Computing builds on various technical developments and is therefore more the result of evolution than revolution: «Cloud Computing» means computing clusters that are connected, which provide uniform and easy-to-use IT environments, thanks to virtualisation, which enable services to be acquired from the most diverse providers and own data to be outsourced from an end device. In the cloud, users can acquire storage space, programmes, server services or whole platforms with configurations and programme interfaces, right up to pre-configured programmes with service goods guarantees and commercial rates. Thanks to virtualisation, users get the impression that they are moving in their own environment, while in fact they are sharing it with other users.

What curbs the Cloud – and what promotes it

Computer scientists often show a certain mistrust towards Cloud Computing. This is not surprising, as Cloud Computing could change their job description; as a matter of fact it contributes to the maintenance and supervision of hardware and software being both sourced outside individual companies. There are also reservations with regards to data security and trust in the providers involved.

Surveys let us conclude that experts with customer contact are more open to the Cloud than computer scientists. They hope for higher flexibility, which is essential especially for individually tailored programmes «on demand». The technical developments should promote a further expansion of the Cloud: rapidly increasing data amounts can be handled better in the Cloud than in fixed installed computing structures, thanks to more flexible capacities. However, cost advantages, which Cloud Computing could realise if necessary, appear to be of minor significance even for the supporters.

Blue sky above...

Expectations for Cloud Computing are great and various trends should promote its further growth. Open interfaces in the Cloud enable new added-value chains, and therefore create conditions for innovative and potentially still unthought-of business models.

From the point of view of smaller companies, Cloud Computing is particularly attractive because they can outsource the maintenance of their IT environment: both storage space and software can be transferred to the Cloud; so it's no longer internal employees who take care of monitoring and updating but rather external specialists. The faster the technology develops, and the more often updates are due, the higher the degree of psychological stress for small companies and private persons, which motivates them to changeover to the Cloud system. Financially the change to the Cloud can also be worth it: apart from a basic fee, often only the specific services, which have been effectively purchased, are billed.

...or cloudy prospects in a vale of mist?

Cloud Computing also leads to new dependencies: if a large provider gets into technical difficulties, then it may bring all companies which have outsourced their information structures onto its platforms into adversity. Experts agree that several risks have not been clarified yet. The Cloud Security Alliance, which declares «best practices» for the security of Cloud Computing in their mission statement, recognizes an important starting point in the training of users of Cloud Computing.

Another dark side of Cloud Computing is that its virtualisation leads to hard-to-understand systems and long, often unknown, dependence chains. Error search is therefore more difficult than with applications that run on clearly allocated servers.

No unsolvable legal problems

Regardless of the data protection concerns, the possible legal problems which could arise with Cloud Computing are completely solvable by suitable contracts.

In particular, a contract must specify the content and quality of the risks, contain security claims and also statements about cancellation possibilities and/or change of offer, including cancellation periods. This means that the services to be provided and their quality must be described, contact persons must be named and plans to recognise risks and their elimination must be worked out and more.

Additionally, it is essential to define access rights, and also determine obligations with regards to guaranteeing data security and/or its restoration. If the delicate points are conscientiously covered and appropriate precautions are taken, Cloud Computing can even offer higher security standards than usual databases.

Switzerland in the clouds?

Whether Cloud Computing opens up special perspectives for Switzerland is controversial, and depends on the point of view. In this country there is no IT tradition, and the willingness to change is not very great – two arguments, that speak against Cloud Computing giving wings to specifically Swiss success stories. On the other hand, the Federal structures could benefit from the use of Cloud Computing, because every

small community must no longer buy its own information pack. The reputation of Switzerland as a reliable partner, which provides high-quality services, could also provide a good basis for business models in the Cloud.

In one point, Switzerland is certainly not a special case: for the Swiss Confederation too, Cloud Computing is not a vague future promise but a form of IT application that is already establishing and asserting oneself even more strongly.

Example

Research Cloud:

In May 2011, IBM Switzerland together with the Swiss Start-Up CloudBroker supported researchers from ETH Zurich in the process of defining the structure of proteins that act against dangerous bacteria. Therefore the researchers were able to make use of 1 million working hours by the Central Processing Unit within one week, hence completing their research much faster. As a highly competitive research country, Switzerland could greatly benefit from Cloud Computing and at the same time offer the best requirements for «Research Clouds».

«Energy-rich» Cloud:

The United Kingdom uses «intelligent» provision with gas and energy in order to reduce consumption and decrease CO₂ emissions. This implies that detailed data are collected. Data amounts collected in this way can only be sensibly managed in the Cloud.

International Cloud:

The EU invested €10.5 million into the research project TClouds of the Seventh Framework Programme (FP7). It aims to develop solutions for data protection and security breakdown of inter-country Clouds. The TCloud infrastructure will be evaluated in the two areas of energy («Smart Energy Grid» on the model of the leading Portuguese energy provider) and health care («Home Healthcare», in collaboration with the San-Raffaele hospital in Milan).

A Cloud for geodata:

For three years the Swiss Federal Office of Topography swisstopo has been using Cloud Computing, on the basis of Amazon offers S3 and EC2. The larger the variability of the demand, the more worth are the advantages of Cloud Computing. Thanks to the concept of «Infrastructure as a Service» swisstopo can rent the currently required capacities at any time – and thereby must only pay for what is needed. The real sticking point is automation, thus in configuration and operating method. This is where the greatest expense is incurred for the ministry. Therefore swisstopo systematically falls back on Open Source software. In contrast to Open Source programmes, the licences of commercial software often restrict use in Cloud Computing environments, or forbid it completely; thanks to Open Source licence management becomes obsolete. Today, swisstopo is in a position to scale the infrastructure horizontally in less than two hours in order to deliver to the customer without delays, even during peak demand – and for more than half a billion objects. Thanks to the selected model «Infrastructure as a Service», swisstopo retains full control of the change management of their services and applications – without having to take responsibility for the physical server, memory and network.

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